

Prescreening Survey

Survey Flow

Standard: Welcome page (1 Question)
Standard: Screening Questions (7 Questions)
Standard: Software Quality (2 Questions)

Page Break

Start of Block: Welcome page

WP

Thanks for taking time to participate in our prescreening survey.

This is a short prescreening survey for an upcoming study. If you qualify for the study, then you will be invited to participate on the second stage.

Sincerely,
The Study team

End of Block: Welcome page

Start of Block: Screening Questions

Q9 Please, enter your Prolific ID:

SQ1 Are you currently working in an agile software development team?

No

Yes

DM3 What is your role in your software development team?

- Software engineer
 - Senior software engineer
 - Tech Lead
 - Solution architect
 - Quality assurance engineer
 - Quality assurance analyst
 - QA Lead
 - Other (please specify below)
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PT2 What agile method do you use in your team?

Scrum

XP

Kanban

SAFe

Other (please specify below)

SQ3 How many years of experience do you have working as a software developer or quality assurance analyst or software engineer?

Less than 5 years

More than 5 years

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DM2 How do you identify your gender?

- Male
 - Female
 - Non-binary / third gender
 - Prefer not to say
 - Prefer to self-describe (please specify below)
-

Q10 Is this statement true or false: Agile is a family of software development methods, inspired from the "agile Manifesto."

- True
- False

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End of Block: Screening Questions

Start of Block: Software Quality

SWQ.1 Throughout this survey we will be asking questions related to software quality. We use ISO/IEC 25010 definition of software quality, which states: “[Software quality is] the degree to which the system satisfies the stated and implied needs of its various stakeholders, and thus provides value”. This ISO model also covers some non-functional characteristics, mainly, “performance “,” compatibility”, ”usability”, ”reliability”, “security”, ”maintainability”, and “portability.” Do you agree with this definition?

- Strongly disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat agree
- Strongly agree

SWQ.2 Please, discuss your response below:

End of Block: Software Quality
